

THE IMPORTANCE OF PUBLIC OPINION IN THE PROCESS OF NORM CREATION

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Abstract: This article analyzes the concepts of "norm creation", "public opinion", ensuring public participation in the implementation of norm creation, the importance of adopting normative legal documents that serve the interests of society, taking into account their opinions, and the reforms implemented in our country in this regard and their dedicated to the results.

Key words: norm creation, public opinion, regulatory legal documents, public control.

Enter: The participation of citizens in the process of creation of norms, their opinions and suggestions are essential for the development of society and the social development of the state. Almost all countries around the world have implemented reforms to ensure human rights and develop democracy, and aim to take into account the opinion of society members and ensure their participation in public administration, law-making, and public affairs in general, and strengthen public control. eating This means the development of the state and society.

In order to understand the main essence of the article, it is advisable to first analyze the essence of some concepts in it.

In order to reveal the concept of norm creativity, comments have been made by various authors in many literatures.

is defined as a number of requirements, rules, methods and methods that must be followed in the process of adopting, formalizing and announcing normative legal documents, making changes and additions to them, and canceling

outdated ones. can be classified as a sum of

Public opinion is a set of thoughts, ideas and views that express the attitude of the majority of society members to the events, reforms, and actions taking place in the state and society. Public opinion is systematically formed in society and changes under various ideological influences. Different thoughts and ideas arise in the society and are exchanged with other ideas and become harmonious. Under the ideas created in the society, the people's goals, dreams and the rights they want to have are gathered. Therefore, taking public opinion into account in the creation of norms is the initial and important part of realizing the demands and wishes of society members.

Public discussion allows to improve law-making activities, ensures that public opinion is taken into account, and also minimizes the possibility of subjective approach to the law-making process by representatives of legislative bodies.¹

of the public in the process of norm creation, we can cite as an example the International Pact "On Civil and Political Rights", which was joined by the Republic of Uzbekistan based on the decision of the Oliy Majlis on August 31, 1995. According to this pact, every nation has the right to self-determination, and the states participating in the pact should encourage all persons in their territory and jurisdiction to exercise this right without any discrimination.²

In our country, a lot of effective work is being done to improve the creativity of norms and take public opinion into account. In particular, Article 36 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan states that citizens of the Republic of

¹ Sherov, Q. P. (n.d.). *NORMATIV-HUQUQIY HUUJATLAR LOYIHALARI MUHOKAMASINI O'TKAZISH TARTIBINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI*. Wikipedia. Retrieved April 17, 2024, from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8188310>

² 16.12.1966. *Fuqaroviy va siyosiy huquqlar to'g'risida*. (n.d.). LEX.UZ. Retrieved April 17, 2024, from <https://lex.uz/docs/-2640479>

Uzbekistan have the right to participate in the management of society ³and state affairs directly and through their representatives. Ensuring citizens' activeness in state affairs, giving them rights in this area and emphasizing them in the main law serve as a basis. In addition, Article 23 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Regulatory and Legal Documents" provides for the generalization and use of various means of determining public opinion, as well as public discussion of draft regulatory legal documents by interested state bodies, citizens. It is set to be held with the participation of self-governing bodies, scientists, experts and citizens. ⁴ This is important in ensuring public interest and transparency.

Article 14 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Public Discussion of Law Drafts" stipulates the announcement of public discussion of draft laws . Narodnoe slovo ” newspapers, no later than ten days after the decision to put them to public discussion was made. It is specified that they can be published in special editions and other mass media. Also, according to this law , it is noted that citizens can freely participate in the national discussion of draft laws, make proposals and comments on draft laws, and have other rights in accordance with the law.⁵

The following opinions expressed by the President of our country, Sh. Mirziyoyev, are a proof of how much the people are given priority in state affairs, law-making and other areas: "All of us should not forget one fact: the people are literally the only source and author of the law. must be. It is necessary to widely

³ *O'zbekiston Respublikasi Konstitutsiyasi.* (n.d.). O'zbekiston Respublikasi Konstitutsiyasi. Retrieved April 17, 2024, from <https://constitution.uz/oz/clause/index>

⁴ *O'RQ-682-coh 20.04.2021. Normativ-huquqiy hujjatlar to'g'risida.* (n.d.). LEX.UZ. Retrieved April 17, 2024, from <https://lex.uz/docs/-5378966>

⁵ *166-II-coh 14.12.2000. Qonun loyihalarining umumxalq muhokamasi to'g'risida.* (n.d.). LEX.UZ. Retrieved April 17, 2024, from <https://lex.uz/docs/-29184>

introduce the procedure of receiving opinions and proposals from below - citizens, local Councils of People's Deputies regarding each draft law. In the process of adopting laws, we should effectively use the system of comprehensive discussion among the population. The leadership of the Oliy Majlis needs to involve the public in the discussion of laws, for this purpose it is necessary to introduce modern information and communication technologies, including creating special "spaces" on the Internet.⁶

Based on the above, we can say that more reforms have been implemented in this field in our country than those implemented by some Western countries.

Methodology: Research done increase in the process one how much social methods , as well as social and legal the field garden without to explain movement done . This is it the article to write in the process different normative - legal documents analysis done and analyzed from the method wide was used . The parts of the subject reflected in the normative legal documents were cited and explained. In addition, a comparative legal analysis was carried out to study the laws and practices of foreign countries related to public opinion and control . In order to ensure the effectiveness of the above analysis, the data collection method was also used.

Results: It should be noted that if the members of the society are not happy and calm in the state, both the state and the society will decline.

For this reason, the reforms listed above are being implemented in our country. Citizens have the opportunity to directly or indirectly express their opinions and conduct public control.

As a result of the referendum held on April 30, 2023, a populist constitution was announced. With its entry into force, citizens got more reliefs and rights .

⁶ O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Shavkat Mirziyoyevning Oliy Majlisga Murojaatnomasi. (2017, December 22). president.uz. Retrieved April 17, 2024, from <https://president.uz/oz/lists/view/1371>

Today, modern techniques and technologies are rapidly developing. As a result, changes are occurring in many areas . In particular, we are feeling the effects of electronicization in state administration. This, in turn, creates an opportunity for citizens and representatives of our society to become more familiar with state affairs, to ensure transparency and prevent corruption. In fact, in the process of creation of norms, a number of conveniences have been created in the issue of public opinion research, and now citizens can familiarize themselves with the accepted laws and regulatory legal documents online, express their attitudes and use such conveniences as submitting objections or suggestions.

Social networks are the most convenient and fast way to convey some information to the population and collect information. Therefore, taking advantage of the opportunity to easily study public opinion, officials who are engaged in legislative initiatives have the opportunity to collect information online by using social networks and conducting various social surveys. they did.

Understanding the concept of public opinion, we can say that it has an impact on the structure and character of society, and determines the level of development and progress of society. The need to take public opinion into account is evident in the process of building a populist and democratic state.

In 1997, the "Social Opinion" public opinion research center was established in Uzbekistan . This center analyzes and summarizes public opinion on social, economic and state policy, government activities.

Discussion: opinion " originated from the English language and was first used in England in the 17th century and has not lost its importance to this day. Many thinkers and scientists have conducted research and research on public opinion. For example, Hegel defined public opinion as an inorganic method of knowing what the people want. In addition, Spanish thinker Ortega Gasset, one of the scientists who deeply studied public opinion, wrote : "The world is ruled by public opinion, it is such a main force that people dominate society . " If we talk

about almost all the sources , the importance of public opinion is emphasized in all of them.

Public opinion is important not only for the development of state management, political and economic development, but it is also a necessary factor for the development of every layer of the society, for the formation of the members of the society, especially the youth, as individuals, and for their maturation based on a certain idea.

Summary: To sum up , public opinion is important not only in the creation of norms, but also in the phenomena manifested in small elements.

should involve citizens in the process of creating norms and establish close cooperation with them, as is the case in every direction and stage of norm creation. It is necessary to follow the established norms. In turn, citizens should refrain from any actions that deviate from the given powers and have a negative impact on the process of creating norms" ⁷(Boymurodov, n.d.).

If we dwell on these points and draw a conclusion, it is not enough for the state to take into account the opinions, suggestions and complaints of citizens. Unfortunately, when such opportunities are created, citizens who use them for the wrong purposes, do not take them seriously and express their opinions based on their own interests are also encountered in practice. For this reason, it is appropriate for society representatives to control their behavior.

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⁷ Boymurodov, B. (n.d.). *Fuqarolarning norma ijodkorligi jarayonida ishtirok etish prinsiplarining nazariy-huquqiy asoslari*. Wikipedia. Retrieved April 17, 2024, from <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6322383>

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